

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of L-sorbose by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate in aqueous acetic acid

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of L-sorbose by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate in aqueous acetic acid 50% (v/v) medium has been investigated. The reaction has been found to be first order with respect to each of the [oxidant] and [substrate] under pseudo-first order conditions. The reaction is catalyzed by acid and a medium of low dielectric constant favors the oxidation reaction. The ionic strength variation does not influence the reaction rate. A 1 : 1 stoichiometry is observed in the oxidation and the reaction rate is not retarded by radical trapping agent, acrylonitrile. The erythrose and glycolic acid have been identified as main products of the oxidation. The effect of temperature is studied and activation parameters are determined. On the basis of kinetic results, a hydride ion transfer mechanism is proposed.

Keywords : L-Sorbose, erythrose, tetraethylammonium chlorochromate.

In carbohydrate chemistry, L-sorbose plays an important role because it is an intermediate compound in the formation of vitamin C. In view of this and because of its special role in biological and food process, kinetic and mechanistic studies on oxidation of L-sorbose has been given a great deal of attention. Tetraethylammonium chlorochromate adds to the selected list of new Cr^{VI} reagents introduced recently as oxidizing agent for the effective and selective oxidation of organic substrate under mild conditions¹. We report here our studies on the oxidation of L-sorbose.

Experimental

Materials : Tetraethylammonium chlorochromate [TEACC] was prepared² by anhydrous chromium(VI) oxide dissolved in 6 M HCl and stirred at 0 °C for 5 min. A solution of tetraethylammonium hydroxide (20% in H₂O) (Lancaster) was added and the resulting orange yellow solid was washed and dried under reduced pressure. Chromium content was determined iodometrically. Solution of L-sorbose was always freshly prepared in aqueous acetic acid 50% (v/v). The ionic strength was maintained constant with the use of concentrated solution of NaClO₄ (C.D.H.). Perchloric acid (C.D.H.) and all other chemicals were used as such without further purification.

Kinetic measurements : The reaction was performed under pseudo-first order condition by keeping a large excess of [L-sorbose] with respect to [TEACC]. The medium of the reaction was always 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water in the presence of perchloric acid. Kinetic measurements were made in Shimadzu UV 160A spectrophotometer at 350 nm. The optical density was measured at various intervals of time. Computation of rate constants was made from the plot of log [TEACC] against time.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of reaction was performed by conducting the oxidation of L-sorbose under the conditions of a known excess of tetraethylammonium chlorochromate. A mixture of L-sorbose (0.01 mol dm⁻³) and TEACC (0.10 mol dm⁻³) was kept for several hours at 30 °C for the reaction to go to completion. The unconsumed oxidant was estimated iodometrically at the end of the reaction. The stoichiometry was found to be 1 : 1 consistent with the following equation

For product analysis the reaction mixture containing L-

sorbose and tetraethylammonium chlorochromate in the stoichiometric proportion 1 : 1 was left as to equilibrate at 30 °C for 24 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized with NaHCO₃, extracted with chloroform, washed with water and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The formation of L-erythrose was confirmed by osazone formation and the presence of glycolic acid was confirmed by spot test³.

Results

The pseudo-first order rate constants were determined at various initial concentrations of reactants. The results obtained are given in Table 1. Plots for different concentrations of tetraethylammonium chlorochromate vs time were linear and the rate constants were independent of initial concentration of tetraethylammonium chlorochromate, showing first order dependence of the rate on [TEACC]. The reaction is first order with respect to [L-sorbose], too. A plot of log k_1 against log [L-sorbose] was linear with a slope of unity thereby confirming first order dependence in [L-sorbose].

Table 1. Rate constant for oxidation of L-sorbose by TEACC at 30 °C

Solvent : Acetic acid-water (50-50% v/v)				
[TEACC] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[L-Sorbose] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] × 10 ¹ (mol dm ⁻³)	k_1 × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)	k_2 × 10 ² (mol dm ³ s ⁻¹)
0.66	1.66	7.73	4.61	
0.88	1.66	7.73	4.60	
1.11	1.66	7.73	4.65	
1.33	1.66	7.73	4.69	
1.55	1.66	7.73	4.68	
1.33	0.33	7.73	0.93	2.82
1.33	0.66	7.73	1.83	2.78
1.33	1.00	7.73	2.80	2.80
1.33	1.33	7.73	3.76	2.83
1.33	1.66	7.73	4.69	2.82
1.11	1.66	3.8	1.74	
1.11	1.66	5.8	3.16	
1.11	1.66	7.7	4.69	
1.11	1.66	9.9	6.68	
1.11	1.66	11.6	8.71	

Rates of oxidation were found to increase with increase in [H⁺] and the slopes of the plots of log k_1 vs log [HClO₄] were approximately unity showing that the reaction is acid catalyzed and follows the first order dependence in [HClO₄].

Consequently the empirical rate law is described as follows :

$$-\frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{L-sorbose}] [\text{TEACC}] [\text{HClO}_4]$$

The reaction rate was not influenced by ionic strength when NaClO₄ was initially added to the reaction mixture over the range 0.83×10^{-1} to 5.00×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³.

When the reaction was initiated by adding acrylonitrile into a solution containing L-sorbose and TEACC, no retardation in the rate was observed. No turbidity due to polymerization of acrylonitrile was observed. Thus, the formation of radical intermediate may be ruled out in the course of the reaction.

Effect of solvent : The reaction has been studied under various compositions of acetic acid-water mixture. It has been observed that the reaction rate increases with the increase of CH₃COOH in acetic acid-water mixture (Table 2). A linear plot between log k_1 and 1/D (inverse of dielectric constant) with a positive slope suggests an interaction between an ion and a dipole⁴.

Table 2. Dependence of rate on solvent composition

[L-Sorbose] = 1.66×10^{-2} mol dm ⁻³ , [TEACC] = 1.33×10^{-3} mol dm ⁻³ , [HClO ₄] = 7.73×10^{-1} mol dm ⁻³ , [NaClO ₄] = 1.66×10^{-1} mol dm ⁻³ , temp. = 25 °C		
CH ₃ COOH : H ₂ O	$k_1 \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	1/D
40 : 60	2.70	0.020
50 : 50	3.47	0.024
60 : 40	4.06	0.028
70 : 30	5.25	0.036
80 : 20	7.90	0.048

The reaction rates at different temperatures were determined and the values of activation parameters were calculated from the slope of linear plot of log k_1 vs 1/T. The data are presented in Table 3. An inspection of data shows that these reactions are characterized by a high negative value of entropy of activation (ΔS^*). This indicates that solvation effect is predominant in the reaction, which suggests the formation of a charged rigid transition state. Furthermore, the high positive value of energy of activation and enthalpy of activation indicate that the intermediate is highly solvated.

Discussion

L-Sorbose exists mainly in α -pyranoid form⁵

Table 3. Temperature dependence and activation parameters of oxidation of [L-sorbose] by [TEACC]

Temp. (K)	$k_1 \times 10^4$ (s^{-1})	E_a ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)	$\log_{10} A$	ΔH^* ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)	ΔG^* ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)	$-\Delta S^*$ ($JK^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$)
293	2.48	-	5.68	49.7	91.7	144.3
298	3.47	47.0	5.67	49.6	92.7	144.6
303	4.69	53.6	5.65	49.6	93.6	145.1
308	7.01	55.6	5.68	49.5	94.1	144.7
313	9.50	-	5.67	49.5	94.9	145.0
		Mean = 52.1 $kJ\ mol^{-1}$			$E_a = 52.1\ kJ\ mol^{-1}$	

There is no evidence of complex formation. Perusal of the UV spectrum of oxidant TEACC without L-sorbose (Fig. 1A) and in the presence of L-sorbose (Fig. 1B) shows no appreciable deviation in the λ_{max} values, but the product formations suggest a mechanism involving intermediate complex formation.

Rate law : Based on the proposed mechanism the rate law for the TEACC oxidation of sugar (S) may be derived as

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[TEACC]}{dt} \propto [\text{Ester}]$$

$$\text{or } -\frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} = k[\text{Ester}] \quad (5)$$

From eqs. (1), (2) and (5)

$$-\frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} = k K_1 K_2 [\text{S}] [\text{TEACC}] [\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} = k [\text{S}] [\text{TEACC}] [\text{H}^+]$$

This mechanism is similar to earlier observation⁶.

Fig. 1. UV-spectra of TEACC in aqueous acetic acid 50% (v/v) (A) and TEACC in aqueous acetic acid 50% (v/v) with L-sorbose (B).

Conclusion :

The oxidation of L-sorbose by TEACC in aqueous acetic acid medium proceeds via hydride ion transfer mechanism involving specific cleavage of C₁-C₂ bond of the substance to give the products.

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